

Enhanced LQR-based Strategy for Seamless Transition Between Grid-connected and Islanded Modes in Microgrids

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Abstract: Ensuring a seamless transition between grid-connected and islanded modes in microgrids is a critical challenge due to transient disturbances during the transition between grid connected and grid islanded control strategies affecting system stability and reliability. This paper presents an advanced control strategy based on a Linear Quadratic Regulator based Smooth Transition Regulator (LQR-STR) to enhance the smoothness and reliability of microgrid mode transitions. Unlike previous approaches, the proposed method integrates the full controller design, including the virtual impedance loop, voltage and current feed forward coefficients in grid-forming operation, and active/reactive power control loops in grid-feeding operation. The impact of imperfect islanding detection and premature reconnection is analyzed, demonstrating the robustness of the proposed method under varying transition conditions. The effectiveness of the approach is validated through detailed simulations in MATLAB/Simulink, showing significant improvements in reducing transient overshoots, enhancing voltage and frequency stability, and ensuring reliable mode transitions.

Keywords: Seamless transition, linear quadratic regulator, grid connected mode, islanding mode, microgrid,

1. Introduction:

Conventional inverter-based microgrids typically employ two kinds of inverter controllers, grid-following inverter (GFLI) controllers and grid-forming inverter (GFRI) controllers. GFLI-based controllers are mostly used during grid-connected operation mode due to their stable operation in stiff grids; however, GFLI suffers from inherent small-signal instability when connected to a weak grid [1] [2]. Conversely, GFRI controllers are widely adopted for islanded operation mode due to their proven stability in weak grid scenarios. However, GFRI controllers

may become unstable when connected to a very strong grid [1] [3]. Therefore, to leverage the advantages of each of these two control systems, the microgrid's inverter controller should work as GFLI in grid-connected mode and GFRI in islanded mode. The primary challenge associated with using different controllers lies in the fluctuations and transient responses that occur during the transition between a GFLI controller and an GFRI controller [4].

Early foundational research in the seamless transition of microgrid operation mode introduced by [5], the authors presented line-interactive inverters to ensure continuous power delivery to loads during grid outages, establishing a basis for seamless transition strategies. Subsequent studies expanded on this concept, focusing on mitigating transient disturbances during mode shifts. Transient signals caused by abrupt switching actions pose significant risks, particularly when controller initialization or switching logic is inadequately designed. Poorly executed transitions can degrade system performance or trigger instability, necessitating advanced control architectures. For instance, [6] developed a synchronization controller with a dual-loop architecture, incorporating an auxiliary control term within the power compensator to suppress transient oscillations.

Similarly, [7] introduced a proportional-resonance controller combined with feedback linearization to counteract switching-induced disturbances, though its reliance on load-shedding compromises reliability. Hardware-oriented solutions, such as the diesel generator-set in [8], leverage inherent mechanical inertia to dampen transition oscillations during extreme grid conditions. While effective, this approach introduces scalability challenges and dependency on fossil-fuel-based resources.

Alternatively, [9] proposed an indirect current control strategy employing cascaded voltage and grid current loops to enable seamless mode transfers without mechanical inertia. Advanced control frameworks, including the linear quadratic regulator (LQR)-based switched control in [10], utilize dual compensators for bumpless transitions. However, such methods neglect phase-locked loop (PLL) dynamics behavior in grid-connected mode and voltage regulation in islanded mode, leaving residual instability risks. Authors in [11] eliminate this issues by including PLL dynamics behavior to the smooth regulator design, However, the proposed method neglected the virtual impedance loop of the GFLI and current and voltage feed forward coefficients of the GFRI affecting the overall system stability in the islanded mode [12]. To enhance robustness, [13] and [14] applied nonlinear robust control techniques with Kalman filters for signal estimation, though their efficacy depends heavily on filter design precision. These methods suffer from computational complexity due to time-variant nonlinearities, limiting practical implementation.

Simpler alternatives, such as the adaptive droop-based voltage controller in [15], prioritize smooth islanding transitions but lack versatility for bidirectional mode shifts. Meanwhile, [16] demonstrated an adaptive internal model control structure validated experimentally, yet its performance hinges on exact plant-model alignment a restrictive assumption in real-world applications. Centralized architectures, as explored in [17], [18], and [19] rely on data exchange between distributed energy resources (DERs) and the point of common coupling (PCC) to coordinate transitions. Distributed control schemes in [20] and [21] further decentralize decision-making but remain vulnerable to communication failures, which can destabilize microgrid operations.

In contrast, decentralized strategies like [22]'s hierarchical sliding-mode controller and [23]'s inverse dynamic model eliminate communication dependencies by embedding adaptive droop compensation and full inverter dynamics cancellation, respectively. While theoretically robust, these methods demand sophisticated computational platforms, underscoring a persistent trade-off between resilience and practicality.

This paper proposed an enhanced LQR-STR method offering a seamless transition between operating modes within the framework of traditional microgrid control systems. This eliminates the need to modify existing controllers and keeps leveraging the advantages of traditional GFLI and GFRI. In other words, many methods have been developed in the literature to achieve the seamless transition between microgrid operation modes; those methods are used to include some modifications to the control systems that make them unsuitable for pre-existing microgrids that utilize conventional GFLI and GFRI.

Conversely, the proposed method in this paper will be able to be added to a pre-existing microgrid and achieve a seamless transition between the operation modes. Unlike the approaches presented in [10] and [11], the proposed method in this paper incorporates a comprehensive controller within the LQR-based smooth transition design. This includes the virtual impedance loop and feedforward coefficients of the grid-forming inverter, as well as the active and reactive power regulation loops of the grid-connected inverter. By accounting for the dynamic behavior of these loops, the proposed approach enhances system performance and stability during the transition process. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as the follow:

- Unlike the approaches in [10] and [11], which overlook the virtual impedance loop and the voltage and current feedforward coefficients in the grid-forming strategy, the proposed method incorporates these dynamic components into the control model and provides a systematic design procedure.

- In contrast to [10] and [11], the proposed method also considers the dynamic behavior of the active and reactive power control loops in the grid-feeding strategy during the reconnection transition.
- To evaluate the robustness of the proposed strategy, the potential impacts of an imperfect islanding detection algorithm and premature reconnection are analyzed for different islanding detection times.

2. Principles of the proposed LQR-STR:

To enable a seamless transition between grid-following and grid-forming control modes, a bumpless transfer strategy using two controllers, an online controller and offline controller is applied. The strategy minimizes the output error between the two controllers, allowing the offline controller to closely track the online controller's output and ensuring a smooth transition during switching. Both controllers are modeled as finite-dimensional, linear, time-invariant systems with complete state feedback, controllability, and observability, making them suitable for applying an LQR-based bumpless transfer method. Real-time inputs and outputs from the online controller are shared with the offline controller to facilitate accurate tracking. During transition, coordinated switching ensures that the offline controller output (U_1) closely matches the online controller output (U_2), with feedback and reference signals (y_1, y_2, r_1, r_2) managed through a smooth regulator (K), as shown in Figure 1. This design effectively maintains operational continuity and minimizes disturbances.

Figure 1 LQR-STR architecture

3. Smooth Regulator Design Procedure:

The primary goal of the smooth regulator is to minimize the difference between the outputs of the online and offline controllers during the transition process. This can be represented mathematically as shown in equations (1) and ((2):

$$E_u(t) = u_1(t) - u_2(t) \tag{1}$$

$$E_e(t) = k(t) - r_1(t) \tag{2}$$

Where, $E_u(t)$ is the error between the outputs of the offline controller (u_1) and the online controller (u_2). $E_e(t)$ is the error between the input signal to the offline controller during the transition (k) and the reference signal for the offline controller (r_1).

To achieve a bumpless transfer, these errors need to be minimized. This requirement is expressed as a cost function ((3), which captures the cumulative error over a specified time horizon T .

$$J(u_2, K) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T (E_u(t)^T W_u E_u(t) + E_e(t)^T W_e E_e(t)) dt \tag{3}$$

where: W_u and W_e are positive definite weighting matrices that determine the relative importance of minimizing $E_u(t)$ and $E_e(t)$. T is the time horizon over which the objective function is minimized.

By following the same procedure in [10] and [11], Equation (3) can be solved for K by solve the Algebraic Riccati Equation (ARE) given by Equation (4

$$PA_m + A_m^T P + PB_m P + C_m = 0 \tag{4}$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} E &= -(D_1^T W_u D_1 + W_e)^{-1} & A_m &= A + B_1 E D_1^T W_u C \\ B_m &= B_1 E B_1^T & C_m &= C^T W_u (I + D_1 E D_1^T W_u) C \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Finally, we can express K as a function of ($x, y_1, u_2, and r_1$) as follows:

$$K = S_f \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y_1 \\ u_2 \\ r_1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{6}$$

Where the smooth regulator state feedback matrix (S_f) is given by:

$$S_f = E \begin{bmatrix} D_1^T W_u C + B_1^T P \\ D_1^T W_u D_2 + B_1^T M Z \\ -D_1^T W_u - B_1^T M Q \\ -W_e - B_1^T M R \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= (A_m^T + PB_m)^{-1}, & Z &= (C^T W_u D_1 + PB_1) E D_1^T W_u D_2 + PB_2 + C^T W_u D_2 \\
Q &= PB_1 E D_1^T W_u + C^T W_u + C^T W_u D_1 E D_1^T W_u, & R &= (C^T W_u D_1 + PB_1) E W_e
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

We observe that the state feedback matrix S_f is a time-invariant matrix, and K become a function of $(x, y_1, u_2, \text{and } r_1)$, which are obtainable from both online and offline controllers. Therefore, switching the offline controller inputs to K enables the offline controller outputs to track those of the online controller, thereby achieving a smooth transition between the two controllers.

4. GFLI to GFRI Smooth Regulator Design.

In the grid-connected mode of operation, the inverter is governed by the GFLI control strategy, while the GFRI controller acts as the offline controller, regulated by the smooth regulator signals, denoted in this case as (K_{IS}) . Our objective is to design a state feedback matrix $(S_{f,IS})$, which will derive the optimal K_{IS} as defined in equation 5

To achieve this objective, we need to define a state-space model of the GFRI controller. As discussed in detail earlier in this chapter, the GFRI control system consists of the current control loop, voltage control loop, primary control loop, and virtual impedance. Figure 2 illustrates the complete block diagram of the GFRI control system, which can be represented as a two-degree-of-freedom (2DOF) system in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{x} &= Ax + B_1 y_1 + B_2 y_2 \\
u &= Cx + D_1 y_1 + D_2 y_2
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where:

- $u = [\theta^* v_{dinv}^* v_{qinv}^*]^T$ represents the controller output signals.
- $y_2 = [P Q i_d i_q v_d v_q i_{dinv} i_{qinv}]^T$ denotes the feedback signals.
- y_1 represents the input signal.

When the GFRI operates as the online controller (Islanded mode), it will receive reference signals as input: $y_1 = r_1 = [\omega^* P^* Q^* E_d^* E_q^*]$. Conversely, in grid-connected mode, the GFRI functions as an offline controller, with its input signals switched to the smooth regulator signals ($y_1 = K_{IS}$).

Figure 2 Full block diagram of the GFRI controller

To facilitate the state space model representation of this system, state variables are defined based on that new state variable after each integrator element in the system (state variable derivative before the integrator element), the defined state variables are illustrated in Figure 2 and given as follow:

$$\dot{x}_1 = -m_p x_2 + \omega^*, \quad \dot{x}_4 = -m_Q x_3 + E^* + i_q X_v - i_d R_v - v_d \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\omega_v x_2 + \omega_v (P - P^*), \quad \dot{x}_5 = K_{pv} \left(\frac{dx_4}{dt} \right) + K_{iv} x_4 + i_d K_{cf} - v_q \omega C_f - i_{dinv} \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = -w_c x_3 + w_v (Q - Q^*), \quad \dot{x}_6 = -i_d X_v - i_q R_v + E_q^* - v_q \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{x}_7 = K_{pv} \left(\frac{dx_6}{dt} \right) + K_{iv} x_6 + v_d \omega C_f + i_q K_{cf} - i_{qinv} \quad (13)$$

Building upon the state variable equations and the block diagram illustrated in Figure 2, the output equations are formulated as follows:

$$\Theta^* = x_1 \quad (14)$$

$$V_{dinv}^* = K_{pc} \left(\frac{dx_5}{dt} \right) + K_{ic} x_5 + v_d K_{vf} - i_{qinv} \omega L_{finv} \quad (15)$$

$$V_{qinv}^* = K_{pc} \left(\frac{dx_7}{dt} \right) + K_{ic} x_7 + i_{dinv} \omega L_{finv} + v_q K_{vf} \quad (16)$$

Combining Equations (10 to 16) and equating their coefficients with the primary 2DOF form presented in Equation (9), the matrices $A, B_1, B_2, C, D_1,$ and D_2 are determined. After the determination of the system matrices, the desired poles of the closed-loop offline system are specified. Accordingly, the optimal weighting matrices W_u and W_e are optimized using the Gradient-Based Optimization approach. Next, the matrices $E, A_m, B_m,$ and C_m are computed from Equation (5). The ARE Equation (4) is then solved to obtain $P,$ after that g is calculated.

Consequently, the matrices M, Z, Q , and R are calculated from Equation (8). Finally, the state feedback matrix of the GFRI $S_{f,IS}$ is computed as follows:

$$S_{f,IS} = E \begin{bmatrix} D_1^T W_u C + B_1^T P \\ D_1^T W_u D_2 + B_1^T MZ \\ -D_1^T W_u - B_1^T MQ \\ -W_e - B_1^T MR \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

5. GFRI to GFLI Smooth Regulator Design.

In the Islanded mode of operation, the inverter is governed by the GFRI control strategy and acts in this mode as an online controller, while the GFLI controller in this mode of operation acts as the offline controller, regulated by the smooth regulator signals, denoted in this case as (K_{GC}). Our objective is to design a state feedback matrix ($S_{f,GC}$), which will derive the optimal K_{GC} as defined in equation (5).

For this objective, initially we need to define a state-space model of the GFLI controller (offline controller). The control block diagram of the GFLI is shown in Figure 3. As outlined in detail earlier in this chapter, the GFLI control system consists of the current control loop, primary control loop, and phase-locked loop (PLL). This control system can be represented as 2DOF system:

Figure 3 Full control block diagram of the GFLI controller

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= Ax + B_1y_1 + B_2y_2 \\ u &= Cx + D_1y_1 + D_2y_2\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

Where in this case:

- $u = [\theta^* v_{dinv}^* v_{qinv}^*]^T$ represents the controller output signals.
- $y_2 = [P Q v_d v_q i_{dinv} i_{qinv}]^T$ the feedback signals.
- And, y_1 is the input signal.

In grid connected mode, GFLI will be operated as an online controller, and it will receive reference signals as input: $y_1 = r_1 = [\omega^* P^* Q^* v_q^*]$. Conversely, in islanded mode, the GFLI functions as an offline controller, where, its input signals switched in this case to the smooth regulator signals ($y_1 = K_{GC}$).

To find appropriate state-space model will repeat same procedure used for GFRI (i.e., new state variable defined after each integrator element in the system and new state variable derivative defined before the integrator element), the defined state variables are illustrated in Figure 3 and defined as follow:

$$\dot{x}_1 = \omega_c(v_q^* - v_q - x_1), \quad \dot{x}_2 = x_1 \quad (19)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = K_{p\theta}x_1 + K_{i\theta}x_2 + \omega^*, \quad \dot{x}_4 = \omega_c(P^* - P - x_4) \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{x}_5 = x_4, \quad \dot{x}_6 = K_{pp}x_4 + K_{ip}x_5 - i_{dinv} \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{x}_7 = \omega_c(Q^* - Q - x_7), \quad \dot{x}_8 = x_7 \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{x}_9 = K_{pp}x_7 + K_{ip}x_8 - i_{qinv} \quad (23)$$

Based on the state variable equations and the block diagram shown in Figure 3, the output equations are derived as follows:

$$\Theta^* = x_3 \quad (24)$$

$$V_{dinv}^* = K_{pc}(K_{pp}x_4 + K_{ip}x_5 - i_{dinv}) + K_{ic}x_6 + v_d - i_{qinv}(\omega L_{finv}) \quad (25)$$

$$V_{qinv}^* = K_{pc}(K_{pp}x_7 + K_{ip}x_8 - i_{qinv}) + K_{ic}x_9 + v_q + i_{dinv}(\omega L_{finv}) \quad (26)$$

Combining Equations (10 to 16) and equating their coefficients with the primary 2DOF form presented in Equation (9), the matrices $A, B_1, B_2, C, D_1,$ and D_2 are determined. Once the system matrices are determined, the desired poles for the closed-loop offline system are identified. Following this, the matrices $E, A_m, B_m,$ and C_m are computed using Equation (5). The Algebraic Riccati Equation (ARE) in Equation (4) is then solved to obtain P , after which g is calculated using

Consequently, the matrices M, Z, Q , and R are derived from Equation (8). Finally, the state feedback matrix for the GFLI ($S_{f,IS}$) is determined as follows:

$$S_{f,GC} = E \begin{bmatrix} D_1^T W_u C + B_1^T P \\ D_1^T W_u D_2 + B_1^T MZ \\ -D_1^T W_u - B_1^T MQ \\ -W_e - B_1^T MR \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

6. Simulation results:

Figure 4 shows the microgrid suggested to evaluate the performance of the proposed LQR-STR approach. This microgrid consists of four inverter-based distributed energy resources (DERs), each DER having an equal capacity of 30 kW and equipped with a VCC-based grid-connected controller and droop control-based grid-forming controller to support dual-mode operation. Additionally, two LQR-based smooth transition regulators have been designed and implemented on each DER to ensure a seamless transition between microgrid operating modes.

The simulation is conducted in the MATLAB/Simulink environment, with the simulation parameters and test case details provided in

Table 1. Two transition scenarios are examined to assess the impact of the inner loop control and phase-locked loop (PLL) dynamics during mode transitions. The effectiveness of the proposed regulators is verified by comparing the results with those obtained without smooth regulators.

Figure 4 Microgrid model for the simulation [10]

Table 1 ELECTRICAL AND CONTROL PARAMETERS OF SIMULATION CASE

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
V_{dc}	650 V	Z_5	$0.0768 + j0.0113 \Omega$
V_{PCC}	325 V	Z_6	$0.0099 + j0.0029 \Omega$
Z_1	$0.0198 + j0.0581 \Omega$	Z_7	$0.0513 + j0.0054 \Omega$
Z_2	$0.1107 + j0.0028 \Omega$	L_1	$5 + j2 \text{ KVA}$
Z_3	$0.0198 + j0.0581 \Omega$	L_2	$50 + j27 \text{ KVA}$
Z_4	$0.0404 + j0.0024 \Omega$	L_3	$20 + j10 \text{ KVA}$
L_4	$22 + j11 \text{ KVA}$		

6.1 *Islanding Transition Scenario:*

The first scenario is an islanding transition scenario. Initially, the microgrid operates in a grid-connected mode, its distributed energy resources (DERs) working at 30% of their nominal power output while maintaining a unity power factor. The islanding event occurs at the $t=2$ seconds, causing the MG to transition into an islanded mode of operation. Upon detecting this transition via a passive islanding detection algorithm with 200 [ms] islanding detection time assumed, the DERs autonomously switch their control strategy to a grid-forming approach.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the active and reactive power dynamics of the INVs during this islanding transition. As depicted in Figure 7, without smooth transition regulator mechanisms, distributed INVs exhibit a notable active power overshoot up to 25% accompanied by prolonged oscillatory behavior. Notably, the proposed Grid-Connected to Islanded LQR-STR further minimizes the maximum active power overshoot across all INVs to below 2.1%, demonstrating a stable and smooth response. Similarly, the reactive power experiences significant overshoots of 21% to 60%, coupled with substantial oscillations when no regulators are employed. These overshoots are improved to less than 15% through the application of the proposed LQR-STR.

Figure 7 illustrates the behavior of the microgrid frequency during the transition. Without smooth regulator, the microgrid frequency exhibits oscillatory behavior and significant overshoot and undershoot between 55.6 to 61.2 Hz. The proposed LQR-STR demonstrates a smooth frequency response with a short settling time, indicating enhanced stability during the transition.

6.2 *Microgrid Reconnection Phase:*

In this scenario, the microgrid will be reconnected to the utility grid at $t = 20$ s. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the active and reactive power dynamics of each distributed inverter during this reconnection transient. Without STR, the INVs exhibit significant transient overshoot in both

active and reactive power. Conversely, the implementation of the proposed Islanded to Grid-Connected LQR-STR facilitates a smooth transition for both active and reactive power with the significant reduction in the overshoot, undershoot, and the oscillations during the reconnection transition.

Figure 5 Active power during grid disconnecting

Figure 6 Reactive power during grid disconnecting

Figure 7 Microgrid frequency during grid disconnecting

Figure 10 illustrates the temporal evolution of the microgrid frequency during the reconnection transition. Subsequent to the reconnection event, the microgrid frequency at PCC experience a transient overshoot up to 63.8 Hz. The proposed LQR-STR significantly reduced the overshoot and demonstrates a smooth frequency response with a short settling time, indicating enhanced stability during the transition.

Figure 8 Active power during reconnecting to the grid

Figure 9 Reactive power during reconnecting to the grid

Figure 10 Microgrid frequency during reconnecting to the grid

7. Conclusion

This paper presents an LQR-based seamless transition control for microgrids, ensuring smooth switching between grid-connected and islanded modes while minimizing transients' disturbances. The proposed strategy effectively enhances system stability and reliability. Simulation results confirm its effectiveness in reducing oscillations and improving performance during the mode transition. Future work may focus on real-time implementation and further optimization for varying grid conditions.

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References:

- [1] P. Liu, X. Xie, and J. Shair, "Adaptive Hybrid Grid-Forming and Grid-Following Control of IBRs With Enhanced Small-Signal Stability Under Varying SCRs," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 6603–6607, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2024.3373659.
- [2] J. Shair, X. Xie, W. Liu, X. Li, and H. Li, "Modeling and stability analysis methods for investigating subsynchronous control interaction in large-scale wind power systems," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 135, p. 110420, 2021.
- [3] F. Zhao, X. Wang, and T. Zhu, "Power dynamic decoupling control of grid-forming converter in stiff grid," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 37, no. 8, pp. 9073–9088, 2022.
- [4] D. E. Olivares *et al.*, "Trends in microgrid control," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1905–1919, 2014.
- [5] R. Tirumala, N. Mohan, and C. Henze, "Seamless transfer of grid-connected PWM inverters between utility-interactive and stand-alone modes," in *APEC. Seventeenth Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (Cat. No. 02CH37335)*, IEEE, 2002, pp. 1081–1086.
- [6] Y. Li, D. M. Vilathgamuwa, and P. C. Loh, "Design, analysis, and real-time testing of a controller for multibus microgrid system," *IEEE Trans. power Electron.*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 1195–1204, 2004.
- [7] T. H. Nguyen, K. Al Hosani, N. Al Sayari, and A. R. Beig, "Seamless transition scheme between grid-tied and stand-alone modes of distributed generation inverters," in *2017 IEEE 3rd*

- International Future Energy Electronics Conference and ECCE Asia (IFEEC 2017-ECCE Asia)*, IEEE, 2017, pp. 344–349.
- [8] B. Singh, G. Pathak, and B. K. Panigrahi, “Seamless transfer of renewable-based microgrid between utility grid and diesel generator,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 33, no. 10, pp. 8427–8437, 2017.
- [9] Z. Liu and J. Liu, “Indirect current control based seamless transfer of three-phase inverter in distributed generation,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 29, no. 7, pp. 3368–3383, 2013.
- [10] D. Das, G. Gurralla, and U. J. Shenoy, “Linear quadratic regulator-based bumpless transfer in microgrids,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 416–425, 2016.
- [11] M. Ganjian-Aboukheili, M. Shahabi, Q. Shafiee, and J. M. Guerrero, “Linear Quadratic Regulator Based Smooth Transition between Microgrid Operation Modes,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 4854–4864, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2021.3094419.
- [12] N. Mohammed, H. Udawatte, W. Zhou, D. J. Hill, and B. Bahrani, “Grid-forming inverters: A comparative study of different control strategies in frequency and time domains,” *IEEE Open J. Ind. Electron. Soc.*, vol. 5, pp. 185–214, 2024.
- [13] S. Fekri, M. Athans, and A. Pascoal, “Robust multiple model adaptive control (RMMAC): A case study,” *Int. J. Adapt. Control Signal Process.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–30, 2007.
- [14] N. Sadati, M. Hosseinzadeh, and G. A. Dumont, “Multi-model robust control of depth of hypnosis,” *Biomed. Signal Process. Control*, vol. 40, pp. 443–453, 2018.
- [15] M. Ganjian-Aboukheili, M. Shahabi, Q. Shafiee, and J. M. Guerrero, “Seamless transition of microgrids operation from grid-connected to islanded mode,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 2106–2114, 2019.
- [16] S. Yazdani, M. Ferdowsi, and P. Shamsi, “Internal model based smooth transition of a three-phase inverter between islanded and grid-connected modes,” *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 405–415, 2019.
- [17] C.-L. Chen, Y. Wang, J.-S. Lai, Y.-S. Lee, and D. Martin, “Design of parallel inverters for smooth mode transfer microgrid applications,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 6–15, 2009.
- [18] A. Micallef, M. Apap, C. Spiteri-Staines, and J. M. Guerrero, “Single-phase microgrid with seamless transition capabilities between modes of operation,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 2736–2745, 2015.
- [19] J. Kim, J. M. Guerrero, P. Rodriguez, R. Teodorescu, and K. Nam, “Mode adaptive droop control with virtual output impedances for an inverter-based flexible AC microgrid,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 689–701, 2010.
- [20] Y. Du, H. Tu, and S. Lukic, “Distributed control strategy to achieve synchronized operation of an islanded MG,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 4487–4496, 2018.
- [21] X. Hou *et al.*, “Distributed hierarchical control of AC microgrid operating in grid-connected, islanded and their transition modes,” *Ieee Access*, vol. 6, pp. 77388–77401, 2018.
- [22] Y. A.-R. I. Mohamed, H. H. Zeineldin, M. M. A. Salama, and R. Seethapathy, “Seamless formation and robust control of distributed generation microgrids via direct voltage control and optimized dynamic power sharing,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 1283–1294, 2011.
- [23] J. Wang, N. C. P. Chang, X. Feng, and A. Monti, “Design of a generalized control algorithm for parallel inverters for smooth microgrid transition operation,” *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 62, no. 8, pp. 4900–4914, 2015.
- [24] F. L. Lewis and V. L. Syrmos, “Optimal control,” *Wiley New York*.
- [25] M. C. Turner and D. J. Walker, “Linear quadratic bumpless transfer &,” vol. 36, no. March 1999, pp. 1089–1101, 2000.